

The MOORCO Experiment :
using long-term experiments to assess the potential of
trees to help achieve net zero.

Ruth Mitchell
and
many others

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Climate crisis

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CAT warming projections
Global temperature increase by 2100

November 2021 Update

GLASGOW LEADERS' DECLARATION ON FORESTS AND LAND USE

working collectively to halt and reverse forest loss

B

CLIMATE CHANGE PLAN The Third Report on Proposals and Policies 2018-2032

February 2018

FORESTS: KEY TO A SUCCESSFUL PARIS AGREEMENT

Forests are a key part of the global carbon cycle. The trees within them if so they age or are cut down. Deforestation and forest degradation emissions after the re-estimated trees, plants and ships in the world.

If current trends continue over the next 15 years, 11 of the world's most ecologically important forest landscapes will be lost.

We will not be able to close the emissions gap or address climate change if we do not agree to the Paris Agreement. Appropriate measures also must be included, so most of the world's deforestation is caused by expanding agriculture.

FOREST AND CLIMATE PROGRAMME

LEARN WHERE WE WORK WHAT WE DO ABOUT WWF SUCCESS STORIES WHAT YOU CAN DO

A TRILLION TREES

Our vision for a trillion trees to be restored, saved from loss, and better protected around the world, by 2050.

Adequate and predictable finance for reducing emissions from deforestation and degradation in developing countries (REDD+) is needed in the agreement if we sustainable development goals.

Money is needed for a variety of approaches, such as properly managing protected areas, improving institutional to prevent illegal logging and strengthening forest governance.

Funding for all forest conservation initiatives, including REDD+, must be the right of indigenous people and local communities to their land and way of life.

The public sector plays a leading role in reducing deforestation and cannot solve the issue alone, especially at the pace that is needed.

Companies in the private sector must also play a role by joining their "deforestation-free" commitments - must provide and source food and commodities - to life in a fair and effective manner.

Forest conservation strategies created and implemented by national governments via REDD+, can be the foundation for the private sector to meet its commitments.

The global forest restoration potential
Potential to store 133.2 to 276.2 GtC

Source Basin et al 2019 Science & erratum

canopy cover

In the UK planting 30,000 ha a year by 2025

England

Spend over £500 million of the on trees and woodlands in England between 2020 and 2025

TOUR FORCE FOR OUR PLANET
The England Trees Action Plan 2021-2024
May 2021

UK Government

Scotland

Increase forest and woodland cover to 21% of the total area of Scotland by 2032

Wales

Woodland cover in Wales increases by at least 2000 hectares per annum from 2020 to 2030

Northern Ireland

A steady expansion of tree cover to increase the many diverse benefits that forests provide.

Global terrestrial ecosystems

Global stock (a) and mass (b, per 5° latitude) of organic carbon in the top 1 m of the terrestrial soil calculated from HWSD v.1.1-adjusted.

Bradly et al. (2005)

A soil carbon and land use database for the United Kingdom

UK Soil Carbon Stocks

Figure 2. Density (kg m^{-2}) of soil carbon in each 1×1 km grid cell in the United Kingdom.

What contribution can new woodlands make to carbon storage?

- Wide range of outcomes
- If carbon is a priority then **many areas do not deliver** or **do not deliver quickly enough**
- Assumes standard establishment methods
- Losses could be less if **soil disturbance** less – e.g. **natural regeneration**

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**Natural regeneration/less soil
disturbance
– no soil carbon losses?**

Utilizing long-term experiments

Miles planted plots

Heather control
plots

Birch plots

- ❖ Established early 1980's
- ❖ 3 sites
- ❖ Each site 6 plots planted birch and 6 open moorland

2005 New experiment

Tree species effects: contrast birch and pine
Impact of grazing

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No soil carbon losses with planting trees with minimal soil disturbance?

- Birch and Pine 12 years old
- Birch trees 39 years old

Results – impacts on carbon storage

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Friggens et al. 2020

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Results – impacts on carbon storage

- Above ground – increase in carbon
- Below ground – losses of carbon
- Overall no net gain in carbon

Summary

- Below ground impacts of trees very important
- On decadal timescales, trees were not mitigating climate change

Does restoring native forest restore ecosystem functioning? Evidence from a large-scale reforestation project in the Scottish Highlands

Emily Warner^{1,2}, Owen T. Lewis³, Nick Brown¹, Rowan Green^{1,3,4}, Alan McDonnell⁵, Doug Gilbert⁵, Andy Hector¹

LETTER

A tipping point in carbon storage when forest expands into tundra is related to mycorrhizal recycling of nitrogen

Karina Engelbrecht et al

Above ground tree carbon

Top soil carbon

Carbon stocks

A landscape photograph showing a row of young, green trees in the foreground, with a fence and more trees in the background under a cloudy sky. The text is overlaid on the lower-left portion of the image.

Questions

Where is that soil carbon going?

What are the mechanisms for the soil carbon loss?

Carbon losses – soil water

Carbon losses – soil respiration

- Extra heterotrophic respiration?
- Organic matter being primed by rhizosphere inputs?

Friggens et al. 2020

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Evidence of priming:

Decomposition

Mitchell et al. (2007 & 2010)

Karina Engelbrecht et al

Changes in nutrient cycling:

Nitrogen mineralisation

Priming of soil fauna?

Mites

Springtails

Soil Microbial
community

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Calluna dominated

Birch/Pine dominated

Lindahl et al. (2021)
 Clemmensen et al. (2015, 2021)
 Friggens et al. (2020)

Mitchell et al (2007, 2009)
 Engelbrecht et al (2021)

Relevance to policy

- Soil carbon losses even with minimal soil disturbance
- Need to consider the whole system
- Experiment time scales \approx Net zero timescales of 2045
- No net carbon gain for tree planting on organic rich soils – a major soil type in Scotland

However

- Mineral soils likely to lead to net gain
- Differences between tree species
- Other benefits e.g. biodiversity

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This project receives funding under the Forestry Grant Scheme.

The Forestry Grant Scheme

Scotland's woodlands and forests are a vital national resource and play an important role in rural development and sustainable land use. As well as helping to reduce the impacts of climate change and providing timber for industry, our forests enhance and protect the environment and provide opportunities for public enjoyment.

The Forestry Grant Scheme funding is supported by the European Union, is supporting the sustainable management of existing woodlands and the creation of new woodlands – contributing towards the Scottish Government's published targets for woodland creation.

Forster Woodland Creation

This is a Forestry Grant Scheme (FGS) funded commercial planting which delivers a UKFS woodland by creating a commercial conifer woodland on land which is suitable for timber production and is accessible for timber transport. This planting will help deliver the outcomes set out in the Scottish Forestry Strategy.

This forest is being managed through deer exclusion, weeding and replacement of dead trees to ensure successful establishment. This woodland captures and stores carbon and will provide a sustainable supply of timber in the future.

The European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development:
Europe investing in rural areas

Scottish
Woodlands

01738 625 128

Challenges the assumption held in many policy circles that tree planting will always mitigate climate change

Answering today's questions with yester-years experiments and passing on the baton to future generations

1975 1980 1985 1990 1995 2000 2005 2010 2015 2020 2025

Thank you to you for listening and...

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And many other

The Funders

- Nature Conservancy
- ITE/CEH/NERC
- British Ecological Society
- Strategic Research Programmes of the Scottish Government.

The Landowners

- Ballogie Estate
- Invercauld Estate
- RSPB
- Crown Estate

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